

THE NEGATIVE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF THE COAL INDUSTRY AND THE ANALYSIS OF CONTAMINATED SOILS AND WATER MICROORGANISMS AT THE 'SHARGUN COAL' JSC MINE IN SURKHANDARYA REGION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the harmful environmental impacts of coal mines and the coal industry on a global scale. It analyzes microorganisms that inhabit areas of coal mines and are directly affected by coal. The study includes primary monitoring of the contaminated soils at the "Sharg'un Coal" production enterprise, aiming to investigate soil microbiota and to isolate and identify the most important and common microbial representatives. The use of microorganisms for bioremediation of nature damaged by coal is recommended.*

Keywords: *coal, mines, shafts, soil, water, analyses, microorganisms, analysis, MALDI-TOF, numbers, identification.*

The coal industry is one of the key sectors that has made a significant contribution to the economic development of countries worldwide. However, coal mining and its utilization have a considerable negative impact on land resources and cause extensive environmental problems, including the loss of vegetation and soil systems, landscape alterations, disruption of the hydrological regime in soils, as well as a decrease in soil fertility and productivity, as noted in previous studies [1]. During the coal mining process, waste rocks are deposited into the earth's layers, resulting in the formation of accumulations with excessively high concentrations of toxic heavy metals. Microorganisms and enzymes, as biological components of the soil, play a vital role as the primary driving forces in soil biogeochemical cycles and as key elements influencing biochemical reactions [2]. Therefore, the diversity of soil microflora and enzymatic activities (dehydrogenase, glucosidase, alkaline and acid phosphatase, urease, invertase, polyphenol oxidase, and others) have been used as indicators for monitoring nutrient cycling and soil energy-dependent processes [3]. Currently, research is primarily focused on studying the negative impact of mechanized coal mining on soil microflora. However, despite this, studies on the adverse effects of coal mine waste on the microbiological, physiological, and metabolic processes in environmental soils are insufficient [4]. In the studies by Kumari and Maiti, the main functions of soil microorganisms, such as nitrogen (N) transformation in coal-mined soils, have been investigated, providing valuable insights into the bioremediation of these areas [5].

In the multilayered coal mine in New Zealand, biological and geochemical methods were used to analyze the microflora. The abundance and activity of microbial populations vary depending on lithology, depth, and substrate [6]. In many regions of China, high-throughput sequencing technology has been used to study the diversity of microbial communities in coal seams [7]. Mining activities affect microbial biomass and the diversity of coal seams. For example, surface air flows into the coal mine, influencing oxidation-reduction reactions at various locations within the mine and enhancing the turnover of different types of microbes. The impact of coal

mining activities on microbial communities in coal seams has been largely underexplored, and there is a lack of research on the diversity and functions of microorganisms in coal seams across various mining regions. Coal seams could serve as a "seed bank" for various microorganisms with diverse functional potentials [8]. The study of the characteristics of microflora in various parts of coal mines has provided technical guidelines for screening functional bacteria with high degradation capabilities, such as resistance to pressure, high temperatures, and radiation. Additionally, key data have been provided for monitoring methane degradation, controlling hazardous events like gas explosions, and reducing carbon emissions in coal mines. Furthermore, studying the distribution range of pathogenic bacteria is considered essential for maintaining the occupational health of individuals working in coal mines.

Coal mining typically generates large amounts of mine water, leading to the contamination of groundwater [9]. Identifying the hydrochemical characteristics of mine water and the factors influencing them helps prevent and control groundwater contamination in coal mining areas. In groundwater systems, microflora play a crucial role as one of the key factors in substance cycling, energy exchange, and other processes in biogeochemical cycles [10]. The conducted studies have explored the important role of microflora in environmental changes in mining areas, as well as the impact of mine drainage on the composition of microflora and hydrochemical properties, affecting surface ecosystems such as soils and rivers [11]. Microbial activity is primarily influenced by redox-sensitive compounds in mine water, including SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , NH_4^+ , Fe, Mn, and others [12]. As of today, the existing literature on coal microbiology primarily focuses on the various microbial community structures, their physiology, ecology, and their activity in coal biodesulfurization processes, as well as the biogenic production of coal bed methane. Initially, many microbial strains were directly isolated from coal environments; however, to achieve effective results, it is crucial to consider the sustainable exploitation of coal resources, their ameliorative condition, and the interrelationships of microbial isolates. Intuitively, when coal is present, the natural microflora in the environment adapts optimally to the surroundings, meaning that they exhibit higher coal degradation efficiency compared to exogenous microflora. Microorganisms living in coal environments feed on coal residues as a carbon source, breaking down the coal and leading to degradation [13].

Research Objects

The experiments were conducted to study the microflora present in soil and water samples from the Sharg'un coal mine in Surkhandarya region, evaluating their quantity and quality indicators. The soils taken from polluted sources during the processes of coal mining, collection, transportation, and consumption exhibited high salinity levels, as indicated by the chemical properties of the samples. Soils collected from the 0-5, 5-15, 15-30, and 30-60 cm horizons were found to belong to chloride, sulfate, phosphate, and carbonate salinity types, with variations in their quantities.

Specifically, in the upper layers of soil (0-5 cm and 5-15 cm), the predominant salts are carbonate and chloride, with lesser amounts of sulfate and phosphate salts (chloride type of carbonate salinity). In the 15-30 cm and 30-60 cm horizons, phosphate salts, silicates, and calcites are more commonly found (phosphosilicate type of salinity). The pH of the soils is high, with values greater than 8.9.

This article presents a study of the microbiological condition of soil and water at the "Sharg'un Coal" JSC mine in Saraosiyoy district of Surkhandarya. Initially, a visit was made to the

"Sharg'un Coal" JSC mine, where soil and water samples were collected from the designated excavation areas. The collected samples were analyzed in the laboratory, and the soil samples were diluted using appropriate methods. To identify soil microorganisms, the prepared suspensions were diluted 2 and 5 times, and then plated onto Chapek agar and Nutrient agar media. The growth of microorganisms in the water and soil samples from the "Sharg'un Coal" production zone was monitored every 24 hours. Three days after the appearance of microbial colonies, the number of colonies in each Petri dish was counted (Table 1). Subsequently, homogeneous colonies were isolated from each dish and transferred to separate agarized nutrient media, which were prepared according to standard microbiological methods. The research results revealed that at the foothills, near the entrance to the coal mine shaft, the soil samples collected from a depth of 5 cm contained 575×10^5 microorganisms, while at a depth of 30 cm, the number of microorganisms was 387×10^5 . Furthermore, soil samples taken from a depth of 5 cm along the coal road, located 50 meters away from the mine shaft, contained 553×10^5 microorganisms.

Table 1. Results of the study on the number of microorganisms grown in contaminated soil samples.

Names of the study areas from which soil samples were collected	Appearance of the grown colonies	The total number of microorganisms
A soil sample was collected from a depth of 5 cm at the point of entry to the coal mine		N = 575×10^5
A soil sample was collected from a depth of 30 cm at the point of entry to the coal mine		N = 387×10^5
A soil sample was collected from a depth of 5.0 cm, located 50 meters from the mine shaft.		N = 553×10^5
A soil sample was collected from a depth of 5.0 cm, located 100 meters from the mine shaft.		N = 317×10^5
A soil sample was collected from a depth of 30 cm, located 100 meters from the mine shaft.		N = 504×10^5

It has been found that the soil sample taken from a depth of 5 cm at the entrance of the coal mine shaft contains a microorganism population of 575×10^5 . In contrast, the soil sample from a

depth of 30 cm at the same location showed a microorganism count of 387×10^5 . Additionally, at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft, the soil sample taken from a depth of 5.0 cm along the coal transport route contained 553×10^5 microorganisms. At a distance of 100 meters from the shaft, the soil sample from a depth of 5 cm along the coal transport route showed a microorganism population of 317×10^5 . Furthermore, at a distance of 100 meters from the site where coal waste accumulates, the soil sample taken from a depth of 30 cm contained 504×10^5 microorganisms. (14)

After the microorganisms in the collected samples showed good growth, their colonies were transferred to test tubes in a pure form and re-cultivated. The species of the microorganisms in the test tubes were identified through MALDI-TOF analysis. The species of the microorganisms grown in the collected samples are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Microbial species identified in soil and water samples collected from the "Sharg'un-Ko'mir" JSC area in Surkhandarya region.

1	Water sample collected from the roadside of the coal transport route (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Pseudomonas veronii</i>
2.	Water directly seeping from the mountain at the entrance of the coal mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Glutamicibacter arilaitensis</i>
3	Soil sample taken from a depth of 5.0 cm at the entrance of the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Pseudomonas chlororaphis</i>
4.	Water sample collected from a distance of 150-200 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on Chapek medium).	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
5	Soil sample taken from a depth of 30 cm at the entrance of the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Acinetobacter vivianii</i>
6	Soil sample taken from the surface at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Kocuria rosea</i> <i>Mycobacterium avium</i> <i>Bacillus simplex</i>
7	Soil sample taken from a depth of 5 cm at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Pseudarthrobacter oxydans</i>
8	Soil sample taken from a depth of 30 cm at the entrance of the mine shaft (cultured on Chapek medium).	<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>
9	Soil sample taken from a depth of 5 cm at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on Chapek medium).	<i>Pseudomonas stutzeri</i>
10	Soil sample taken from a depth of 5 cm at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium, 2nd dilution).	<i>Pseudomonas koreensis</i> <i>Bacillus vallismortis</i>
11	Soil sample taken from the surface at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on Chapek medium, 2nd dilution).	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>

12	Soil sample taken from the surface at a distance of 50 meters from the mine shaft (cultured on nutrient agar medium).	<i>Bacillus pumilus</i>
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As a result of the research, the culture of *Glutamicibacter arilaitensis* was found in water samples collected directly from the mountain at the entrance of the coal mine shaft, as well as in water from the coal transport route, and at a depth of 5.0 cm in soil located 50 meters from the mine shaft. Furthermore, another commonly found species, *Pseudomonas chlororaphis*, was prevalent in the water samples taken from the roadside of the coal transport route, as well as in soil samples from the entrance of the mine shaft at depths of 5.0 cm and 30 cm. The culture of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was isolated from samples taken at a depth of 5.0 cm and 30 cm at both the entrance of the mine shaft and at a distance of 50 meters from the shaft.

Based on our experiments, species such as *Bacillus simplex* and *Bacillus cereus*, which are noted in foreign literature as highly active and possessing significant destructive capabilities, were also found to be widely distributed in the study area. These species were primarily observed in water samples taken from distances of 50, 150, and 200 meters from the coal mine, as well as in soil samples at various depths. It was noted that these species play a significant role in the bioremediation of the area surrounding the coal mine. [15]

The data obtained from our study aligns with the information found in the literature. Thus, due to the contamination of the soil by coal residues and dispersive acids, a significant number of microbial colonies were identified in the studied soils. The interactions between microbial species and the coal environment are among the most important factors for the high degradation and utilization of coal, as they serve as relatively favorable microbial substrates.

The heterogenic and aromatic-condensed structure of coal is not yet fully understood from the perspective of its bioeffectiveness, as coal-microbe interactions are complex. The application of various microorganisms to coal for beneficial purposes will depend on their metabolic and functional characteristics in the subsequent stages. Future research will continue to focus on analyzing the biology of the aforementioned species and selecting the most effective ones for the bioremediation of coal-impacted areas.

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